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FEASIBILITY STUDY OF GROWING ENERGY CROPS IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to consider results of a feasibility study of two bioenergy projects related to energy crops. The projects include growing willow and miscanthus, production of biomass chips and their supply to biomass boiler plants. Such projects can be a typical and effective option for the replacement of expensive fossil fuels in Ukraine, first of all, natural gas. Ukraine has a big area of unused or degraded agricultural land, roughly about 3...4 Mha. This land can be used for cultivating energy crops not competing with the production of food and feed. Of this available area, now only about 6,000 ha are occupied by the plantations, mainly those of willow and miscanthus. This is due to the fact that the existing economic conditions are not always favourable for the implementation of such projects in Ukraine, and therefore the sector does not attract much investments. The Bio-energy Association of Ukraine developed and suggested a number of instruments aimed to encourage and support projects on growing energy crops in the country. The suggested incentives were included in two draft laws which are registered in Ukrainian Parliament.

Keywords: renewable energy, biomass, biomass potential, energy crops, feasibility study.

Introduction.

Green energy transition is a vitally important global trend that contributes to the world economy decarbonization and climate change mitigation. The transition to renewable energy sources (RES) is one of the primary tasks for Ukraine's energy sector which still heavily relies on fossil fuels including the imported ones. According to the last available Ukraine's Energy Balance (2020), the shares of natural gas, coal and nuclear energy in the total primary energy supply (TPES) are 27.5%, 26.4% and 23.1%, respectively. The rest is oil (16.4%) and RES (6.6%). The current share of renewable energy in TPES is obviously too low for a country with a huge potential of RES including biomass.

Several strategic documents set important national targets for the development of renewable energy and wider use of low-carbon energy carriers in Ukraine. The target stated in the National Economy Strategy until 2030 is 25% of RES in the total power production. According to the Heat Supply Concept, the contribution of alternative energy sources (including RES) to heat production is planned to be 40% in 2035. Ukraine's National Transport Strategy until 2030 sets an ambitious

goal to reach 50% share of alternative energy sources (including RES) and electricity in the transport sector energy consumption. All the goals set for renewable energy can be achieved only on condition of considerable contribution of bioenergy, which envisages its more dynamic development (Geletukha 2021).

Ukraine has a considerable potential of biomass available for energy production, which is about 26 Mtoe/y (the economic potential). The share of energy crops in the biomass potential is 21%. They include wood and grass crops for solid biomass fuel, oil crops for biodiesel and maize silage for biogas production (Table 1). By 2050, the biomass potential may double with the share of energy crops increased to 26%. Main key factors for the growth comprise the doubled area under wood/grass energy crops, as well as increased yields of these crops and maize silage intended for biogas. It is expected that in 2050, 10% of the theoretical potential of wood/grass energy crops will be used to produce biomethane via thermochemical gasification of biomass. In addition, it is assumed that in 2050, biodiesel will be produced from oil energy crops grown on unused agricultural land or land of low productivity (Geletukha 2023).

Table 1.

Current and prospective potential of energy crops in Ukraine.

Type of energy crop	Theoretical production potential ¹⁾	Potential available for energy (the economic potential)		
		Share of the theoretical potential, %	Mtoe/y	Share of the total biomass potential, %
Wood/grass energy crops (such as willow, poplar, miscanthus) for solid biomass fuel:	Mt/y			
2021 (0.5 Mha) ²⁾	6.00	100	2.58	10
2050 (1 Mha) ³⁾	18.00 ⁴⁾	90	6.96	16
Oil energy crops (such as Camellina) for biodiesel:	MI/y			
2050 (0.5 Mha)	360	100	0.29	1
2050 (1 Mha)	720	100	0.58	1
Maize silage for biogas:	Bm ³ CH ₄ /y			
2021 (1 Mha)	3.00	100	2.57	10
2050 (1 Mha)	3.75 ⁵⁾	100	3.22	8
Wood/grass energy crops (such as willow, poplar, miscanthus) for biomethane:	Bm ³ CH ₄ /y			
2050 (1 Mha) ³⁾	5.63	10	0.44	1
Total for 2021 (the current potential)			5.44	21%
Total for 2050 (the prospective potential)			11.20	26%

1) The theoretical potential is calculated as a total amount of biomass fuel/biofuel that can be produced from the respective energy crops.

2) Here and further in the table, it is the area under respective energy crops.

3) It is expected that in 2050, 10% of the theoretical potential of wood/grass energy crops will be used for biomethane production via biomass gasification.

4) The assumed increase of energy crops yield is 1.5 times in 2050.

5) The assumed increase of energy crops yield is 1.25 times in 2050.

Energy crops are dedicated plants that are cultivated for the production of energy and biofuels. An important advantage of energy crops is the possibility of growing on marginal, degraded and contaminated land. As a result, the cultivation of energy crops does not compete with the production of food and feed, as well as contributes to avoiding indirect land use change problems. In addition, energy crops can lessen and remediate land pollution by the disposal of contaminants (Abreu 2022). All these features make the production and use of energy crops sustainable.

Many energy crops do not require much care while growing since they are resistant to low temperature (willow, reed canary grass, switchgrass, poplar, miscanthus) and drought (sorghum spp., switchgrass, giant reed, cardoon, poplar). Most energy crops have medium water requirement, the exceptions being willow, reed canary grass, eucalyptus. Wood and grass energy crops have quite good fuel properties (for example,

heating value and ash melting temperature) which are better than those of straw (Geletukha 2014).

In Ukraine, like in the EU, the potential for growing energy crops is determined mainly by the available area of unused or low productive agricultural land on which energy crops plantations can be created. According to different estimates, this area is 3 to 8 Mha in Ukraine (Tryboi 2023, Ivanova 2016). Now, the area under energy crops in the country is only about 6,000 ha, the main crops being willow and miscanthus. The slow development of this sector is due to the fact that under the current conditions, economic indicators of respective projects are not always attractive for investment (Tryboi 2021). For the more dynamic development in the further, the sector is lacking for some dedicated incentives and support instruments.

Methodology.

The feasibility study covers the case of growing willow and miscanthus with the purpose of production and sale of biomass chips. The chips are intended for the use as fuel at biomass boiler plants. An approximate correlation between the capacity of a boiler plant and the required plantation area of a certain energy crop intended to provide the boiler plant with fuel is presented in Figure 1. The correlation is valid for the following conditions: the heating period is 178 days, boiler efficiency is 85%, nominal load is 70%; willow yield (W50%) is 20 t/ha/y for the 2nd...6th harvesting and 12 t/ha/y for the first and seventh harvesting; miscanthus yield (W20%) is 20 t/ha/y for the 3rd...20th harvesting and 5 (12) t/ha/y for the first (second) harvesting. The biomass of willow is collected each third year, and miscanthus is harvested annually.

Figure 1. Correlation between the capacity of a biomass boiler plant and the required area under energy crops.

The feasibility study is carried out for two options: (1) the existing conditions and (2) availability of a hypothetical state subsidy for growing energy crops. The assumed subsidy of 700 EUR/ha for willow and for miscanthus is counted in capital costs of the respective projects. According to the Bioenergy Association of Ukraine (UABIO), the subsidy is one of possible instruments to effectively support projects on cultivating energy crops in Ukraine (Geletukha 2020).

There are also other possible mechanisms developed and suggested by the Bioenergy Association of Ukraine to support the domestic energy crops sector. They include increasing the term of a land lease agreement to 20 years; simplifying the lease of unproductive land for the cultivation of energy crops (that means the lease without holding land auctions); limiting the maximum amount of rent for unproductive and degraded land on which plantations are located to 5% of their normative monetary value. Such a restriction will prevent an unpredictable change in the rent during the lease term and will have a positive effect on the economic indicators of projects on energy crops cultivation.

Two relevant draft laws were elaborated and registered in Ukrainian Parliament as early as in 2021. One of them lays the legislative foundations for the intro-

duction of a support mechanism. This draft law envisages the stimulation of production and consumption of renewable energy by means of a state subsidy for growing energy crops. The subsidy granting scheme is to be determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. By now, the draft laws have not been considered and adopted yet. Nevertheless, UABIO keeps an eye on them as it considers energy crops to be a very important and promising sector of Ukraine's bioenergy.

Main part.

Results of the performed feasibility study are presented in Table 2. It is assumed that the plantations of energy crops (1200 ha of willow and 400 ha of miscanthus) are situated on leased land. Another assumption of the feasibility study is that 60% of the investment is loan funds with the discount rate 6%. The willow plantation is divided into three plots of 400 ha each; the biomass is harvested annually from one of the three plots in turn. Miscanthus is harvested each year from the whole area of 400 ha. Specific capital cost (per hectare) is higher for the miscanthus plantation: 4250 EUR/ha as compared to 2570 EUR/ha for the willow plantation. This is due to the higher specific cost of machinery and equipment per hectare required for the project implementation. At that the average operating cost is lower for the miscanthus project: 75,000 EUR/y against 148,000 EUR/y for the willow project.

Table 2.

Feasibility study for growing energy crops for biomass chips production in Ukraine.		
Indicators	Willow plantation	Miscanthus plantation
<i>Main characteristics of the plantation:</i>		
Plantation area (leased land), ha	1200	400
Lifetime period, years	21	20
Growing cycle, years	3	1
Plantation area that is harvested annually, ha	400	400
Expected biomass yield, t/ha/y	20 (W50%)	20 (W20%)
Distance to the local storage near plantation, km	2	2
Distance to the central storage, km	25	25
<i>Input economic data of the project:</i>		
Capital cost, 1000 EUR, including:	3083 (2243)*	1700 (1420)*
- machinery and equipment	1400	1145
- seedlings and fertilizers	1683 (843)	555 (275)
Specific capital cost, EUR/ha	2570 (1870)	4250 (3550)
Average operating cost**, 1000 EUR/y	148	75
Share of loan funds, %	60	60
Discount rate, %	6	6
Biomass chips sale price (without VAT), EUR/t	48	72
Price of substituted natural gas (without VAT), EUR/1000 m ³	310	310
Boiler plant capacity, MW	15.2	8.8
<i>Main economic indicators of the project implementation:</i>		
Internal return rate (IRR)	14.7% (18.3%)	17.8% (20.8%)
Net present value, 1000 EUR	4430 (5212)	2353 (2610)
Simple payback period (SPP), years	8.7 (7.6)	6.8 (6.1)
Discounted payback period, years	10.6 (8.9)	8.1 (7.1)
Profitability index	2.4 (3.3)	2.4 (2.8)

* Here and further in the table, the figures in brackets are for the case of 700 EUR/ha state subsidy.

** Operating cost are varying during the plantation lifetime.

Income of the projects in question is determined by the amount and sale price of the biomass chips. Willow and miscanthus are harvested at a different moisture content which is 50% and 20% respectively. Hence, the sale price of biomass chips in the feasibility study is assumed higher for miscanthus: 72 EUR/t (without VAT) as compared to 48 EUR/t (without VAT) for willow. The capacity of boiler plants indicated in Table 2 is in line with the correlation presented in Fig. 1.

Based on all the above input data, the simple payback period (SPP) of the energy crops projects is assessed as 8.7 years (IRR 14.7%) for willow and 6.8 years (IRR 17.8%) for miscanthus. These results are valid for the current conditions. In case of availability of 700 EUR/ha state subsidy, SPP decreases to 7.6 (IRR 18.3%) years for the willow project and to 6.1 (IRR 20.8%) years for the miscanthus project. Without the subsidy, the short enough SPP may be achieved if a company starting the project on growing energy crops already has its own machinery and equipment required for the project implementation. In this case the capital costs are much lower, hence economic indicators are higher: SPP is 6.9 years for the willow project and 3.9 years for the miscanthus project. Profitability indexes of both projects are close to each other being 2.4 for the existing conditions and about 3 for the case of the state subsidy.

Findings.

Growing energy crops is a promising and almost untapped sector of Ukraine's bioenergy. Having on average 3...4 Mha of unused agricultural land, the country uses only about 6,000 ha under energy crops plantations now. The reason is that projects on cultivating energy crops are rather difficult for the practical implementation as they are sensitive to many factors that affect their economic performance. Usually, the simple payback period of such projects is 7...9 years, which is on the verge or even beyond their profitability and economic feasibility. As a result, the projects are not very attractive for investments, especially big ones. The Bioenergy Association of Ukraine has elaborated and suggested several tools for stimulating the development of this sector in the country, one of them being the introduction of a state support. In the presence of subsidy of 700...800 EUR/ha, the payback period of respective projects can be reduced to about 5...7 years, depending on the type of a crop and initial conditions.

Examples of energy crops suitable for Ukraine's soil and climate conditions are willow, miscanthus, poplar, Camelina, maize for silage. The existing now plantations are mainly those of willow and miscanthus. Biomass harvested from the plantations is comminuted and used as fuel at domestic bioenergy plants. For sure, this direction should be further developed; however, another topical area is the production of biogas/biomethane from energy crops, for example, from maize silage. According to UABIO's estimate, the area under

maize as energy crop may reach 1 Mha, which is comparable with the potential area under wood/grass energy crops in the country.

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